

EDUCATIONAL CONTENT IN THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM AND ISSUES OF ITS IMPROVEMENT

Asenbaeva Klara Khudaybergenovna

Director of the State Preschool Educational
Organization No. 3 of the Department of Preschool
And School Education of the Nukus District
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15200928>

Annotation. This article provides insights into reforms, challenges, and solutions in the preschool education system. Preschool education is the primary part of lifelong learning. It stimulates the child's desire to learn, prepares him for systematic learning, ensuring that the child is formed into a healthy and developed person. Therefore, the further strengthening of this system, the creation of favorable conditions in preschool education, the wide involvement of preschool children in them play an important role in the formation of our children as harmonious and mature individuals.

Keywords: preschool, continuing education, primary, child, healthy and developed, person, study, activity, institution.

Expanding the coverage of children with preschool education, further improving the use of preschool education services, ensuring favorable conditions for their full life activity, and actively involving them in social life is our most urgent task.

Large-scale work has also been carried out in the departments of preschool education to raise a healthy and comprehensively developed younger generation, introduce effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process, and organize an effective system of preschool education.

Currently, large-scale reforms are being carried out in the field of education, as in all spheres of our republic. Preschool education is the primary link in the system of continuous education and plays an important role in the upbringing and preparation for school of a comprehensively healthy and harmoniously developed child. Preschool education creates the necessary organizational, methodological, psychological, and pedagogical conditions for raising healthy, comprehensively developed children, and helps parents prepare children for regular school education. In recent years, special attention has been paid to improving the preschool education system, updating the forms, means, and methods of educational content. The state and society have set the task of developing preschool children based on a single requirement. Preschool education, being the primary link in the system of continuous education, plays

an important role in the upbringing and preparation for school of a comprehensively healthy and harmoniously developed child. Over the past period, large-scale work has been carried out in our country to create an effective system of preschool education aimed at raising a healthy and comprehensively developed younger generation, introducing effective forms and methods of education and upbringing into the educational process.

The favorable conditions created for the development of public-private partnerships in the field of preschool education have become a solid foundation for further increasing the number of non-state preschool educational institutions and expanding the range of services they provide. At the same time, the analysis shows the need to solve the issues of ensuring the coverage of children with preschool education, filling preschool educational institutions with modern educational and methodological materials and fiction, and attracting qualified pedagogical and managerial personnel to the sphere.

The favorable conditions created for the development of public-private partnerships in the field of preschool education have become a solid foundation for further increasing the number of non-state preschool educational institutions and expanding the range of services they provide. At the same time, the analysis shows the need to solve the issues of ensuring the coverage of children with preschool education, filling preschool educational institutions with modern educational and methodological materials and fiction, and attracting qualified pedagogical and managerial personnel to the sphere.

In order to further improve the preschool education system, ensure equal access of children to quality preschool education, develop the non-state sector of preschool education services, and also in accordance with the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 30, 2018 No. PP-3955 "On Measures to Improve the Management of the Preschool Education System": further improvement of the regulatory framework in the field of preschool education;

* creating conditions for the comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic, and physical development of preschool children; increasing the coverage of children with quality preschool education, ensuring equal access to it, and developing public-private partnerships in this area;

* introduction of innovations, advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the preschool education system; improvement of the preschool education management system, ensuring transparency and efficiency of financing the activities of preschool educational organizations;

* introduction into the preschool education system of fundamentally new approaches to the training, retraining, advanced training, selection, and development of preschool education system employees;

* it is planned to implement such issues as the introduction of healthy and balanced nutrition of children in preschool educational organizations, quality medical supervision¹.

Implementation of state requirements into practice. However, since this process is complex, it is carried out in stages. The state creates the necessary conditions and opportunities to achieve the indicator specified in the requirements. Children's knowledge, skills, and abilities are checked at the end of each academic year through control exercises. The level of school readiness of children aged 6-7 is checked based on the indicators of these state requirements. Preschool educational organizations, firstly, provide an opportunity for general literacy of preschool children, instilling in them a sense of love for the Motherland, pride in it, studying the Constitution, and broadening their worldview, and secondly, they also serve to realize the constitutional right of mothers with young children to work.

It should be noted that we still have important priority tasks ahead of us in the preschool education system. Our main goal is to further improve the preschool education system, expand the network of preschool educational organizations and strengthen their material and technical base, provide them with qualified teaching staff, introduce modern educational programs and technologies into the educational process for the comprehensive intellectual, spiritual, aesthetic, and physical development of children, and radically improve their level of school readiness.

Preschool education is the initial part of continuous education. It ensures the formation of a healthy and developed personality, awakens the child's desire to learn, and prepares them for systematic learning. Therefore, further strengthening the activities of this system, creating comprehensively favorable conditions in preschool educational organizations, and widely involving preschool-age children in them play an important role in the formation of our children as well-rounded and mature individuals.

References:

1. Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for Further Improvement of the Preschool Education System for 2017 - 2021"
2. Regulation on Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. T-2000
3. Sh.Sodikova Preschool Pedagogy T. Science and Technology 2012

THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

4. F.Qodirova, Sh.Toshpo'latova, M.Azamova. Preschool Pedagogy. Tashkent-2013.

